

Status of Aerothermal Modeling for Current and Future Mars Exploration Missions

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Abstract—The status of aerothermal analysis for Mars entry missions is reviewed. The aeroheating environment of all Mars missions to date has been dominated by convective heating. Two primary uncertainties in our ability to predict forebody convective heating are turbulence on a blunt lifting cone and surface catalysis in a CO₂ environment. Future missions, particularly crewed vehicles, will encounter additional heating from shock-layer radiation due to a combination of larger size and faster entry velocity. Uncertainties inherent in the physical models employed to predict these phenomena are explored. Capabilities of ground test facilities to support aeroheating validation are also summarized. Engineering flight data from the Viking and Pathfinder missions, which may be useful for aerothermal model validation, are discussed. Examples are taken from past, present, and future Mars entry missions, including the twin Mars Exploration Rovers and the Mars Science Laboratory, scheduled for launch in 2009.¹²

European Space Agency (ESA), the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR), and the Russian Space Agency (RSA). As of this writing both NASA Mars Exploration Rovers – Spirit and Opportunity – are still functioning and returning scientific data after more than 19 months on the surface of the planet, and have uncovered compelling evidence that water once existed on the surface. Two additional NASA missions are currently planned: the Phoenix Lander, scheduled for launch in 2007, and the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL), with a launch currently scheduled for 2009. In addition, several NASA programs continue to plan future Mars missions: the Mars Technology Program is actively pursuing the development and selection of technologies to support the next generation of proposed Mars exploration, the Exploration Systems Mission Directorate has plans for eventual robotic technology demonstration missions to Mars to lay the groundwork for possible human expeditions, and the In-Space Propulsion program is investigating the possible use of aerocapture as a means of entering spacecraft more efficiently into Mars orbit than by propulsive deceleration [1].

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1. INTRODUCTION

Fueled by the search for extraterrestrial life, Mars has been the most frequently visited planet in the solar system. No less than thirteen attempts have been made to land on the surface of the red planet (see Table 1) by NASA, the

Of all successful entries to date, only the first two (Viking I and II) have captured into orbit about the planet prior to entry. The decision to enter the Viking spacecraft from Mars orbit was made in part due to concerns about the severity of the entry heating environment in a (then) relatively unknown atmosphere. All subsequent missions have entered Mars directly on a hyperbolic trajectory, which leads to higher entry velocities, and therefore higher heat fluxes and loads, than an orbital entry. This decision lowers the total mass of the spacecraft by eliminating the fuel and propulsion system necessary to perform the Mars Orbit Insertion (MOI) maneuver. However, the thermal protection system (TPS), which shields the spacecraft from the intense heat generated during the entry, becomes more complex as the entry velocity (and therefore encountered heating rate) increases. From Table 1 we see that relative entry velocities (V_{rel}) for these missions have ranged from 5.5–7.5 km/s, with the exact value dependent on the interplanetary orbital

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² IEEAC paper #1428, Version 7, December 10, 2005

Table 1. Summary of Mars entry missions

Flight	Agency	Entry Date	V_{rel} (km/s)	α (deg)	γ (deg)	q_{max} (W/cm ²)	Flight Data?	Ref.	Notes
Mars 2	USSR	Nov. 27, 1971	6.0	0			?	66-67	Lander crashed
Mars 3	USSR	Dec. 2, 1971	5.7	0			?	66-67	Operated for 20 seconds
Mars 6	USSR	Mar. 12, 1974	5.6				?	66	Lander crashed
Mars 7	USSR	Mar. 6, 1974					?	66	Targeting error
Viking I	NASA	Jul. 20, 1976	4.5	11	-17	21	Yes	61	
Viking II	NASA	Sep. 3, 1976	4.5	11	-17	21	Yes	61	
Mars96	RSA	1996					?	66	Launch failure
Pathfinder	NASA	Jul. 4, 1997	7.5	0	-14	120	Yes	34	
MPL	NASA	Dec. 3, 1999	6.9	0	-13	80	No	68	Failed during final descent
DS-2	NASA	Dec. 3, 1999	6.9	0	-13	200	No	69	Lost after separation
Beagle	ESA	Dec. 25, 2003	5.6	0	-16	75	No	70	Lost after separation
MER-A	NASA	Jan. 3, 2004	5.6	0	-12	45	No	71	
MER-B	NASA	Jan. 24, 2004	5.6	0	-12	45	No	71	
Phoenix	NASA	2008	5.5	4	-14	~65	No	–	
MSL	NASA	2010	~5.7	~16	-14	~120	TBD	23	

mechanics of the particular mission opportunity. Still higher velocities (on the order of 7-9 km/s) are possible for future crewed missions [2], for which the desire for reduced mission duration may be more important than minimizing fuel consumption. Also shown in Table 1 for each mission are the entry date, flight path angle (γ), and angle of attack (α), as well as the predicted zero-margin peak heating rate (q_{max}) and a note as to whether the entry vehicle included any engineering instrumentation from which in-situ measurements of the flight aerothermal environment could be obtained.

The design of a low mass and reliable (low risk) TPS system for Martian atmospheric entry requires an accurate prediction of the aerothermal environment encountered. The peak heat flux (along with surface pressure and shear stress) will determine the thermal protection material selected for the heatshield, while the total integrated heat load determines the final thickness of material required. Laminar convective heating has been the primary TPS driver for all Mars missions to date. Turbulent heating, although a potentially large uncertainty, has not been a significant issue for entries thus far. However, the trend toward larger, lifting, higher ballistic coefficient targeted landers (such as MSL) makes transition to turbulence and the resulting heating levels a significant concern for future missions. The long slender (higher L/D) vehicles that will be required for future human missions will also certainly encounter a turbulent heating environment. A second significant source of aeroheating uncertainty is catalytic heating in a dissociated CO₂ atmosphere. Catalysis, in which the TPS surface facilitates the recombination of incident species, can be a large contributor to the total heating rate. No validated model currently exists to accurately predict the catalytic behavior of real Mars TPS materials under flight conditions, and thus conservative assumptions are employed to model this effect. Another potentially significant uncertainty is the

amount of radiative heating, which is produced by the dissociated and ionized species in the hot shock layer in front of the entering spacecraft. The integrated intensity of radiation from the shock layer scales roughly linearly with the size of the entry vehicle, and approximately exponentially with the entry velocity. For all missions to date the largest predicted level of shock layer radiative heating was for Pathfinder (~5-10 W/cm²), due to its 7.5 km/s entry velocity. This level of radiative heating was still small as compared to the approximately 115 W/cm² of convective heating predicted for the Pathfinder entry. However, future missions, particularly crewed vehicles and their precursor cargo missions, will be much larger and will have potentially higher entry velocities, which will lead in turn to much higher radiation levels. Although shock-layer radiation for moderate velocity Earth entries is reasonably well understood, no validated nonequilibrium model currently exists to predict this effect in the Martian atmosphere.

The focus of the current paper is to review the status of aerothermal analysis for Mars entries. Uncertainties inherent in the physical models used to predict these phenomena are explored, and a methodology is discussed by which those uncertainties can be quantified and ranked in importance for TPS design. Examples are taken from past, present, and future Mars entry missions, including Pathfinder, the twin Mars Exploration Rovers (MER), and MSL. Capabilities of ground test facilities, including the hypersonic wind tunnels at NASA Langley as well as high enthalpy shock tunnels at the California Institute of Technology and the CalSpan University Buffalo Research Center, to support aeroheating validation for Mars entry missions are briefly summarized. Finally, the small amount of available engineering data obtained from the Viking, Pathfinder, and MER missions, which may be useful for aerothermal model validation, are discussed, and an argument is made for the need for

additional flight data to support the next generation of ambitious Mars missions. Note that only continuum flow analysis, using computational fluid dynamics (CFD), is presented. Analysis of rarefied (non-continuum) flows is usually performed using Direct Simulation Monte Carlo (DSMC) techniques, which are beyond the scope of this review. An excellent summary of the use of DSMC methods for wake flow computational aerothermodynamics is given by Moss and Price [3]. However, it is important to note that, for most missions of interest that use hard aeroshell and are direct entry rather than aerocapture, the majority of the heat pulse occurs in the continuum flow regime, where traditional CFD methods are valid. Future human missions to Mars will utilize a combination of aerocapture and direct entry strategies and the current work is a step along the way of establishing the fidelity of analysis methods.

2. PHYSICAL MODELS

The Martian atmosphere consists of approximately 97% CO₂ and 3% N₂ by volume. Small amounts of other species (primarily Argon) are also present, but can usually be neglected. The high temperature flowfield behind the bow shock is a region where the gas heats and dissociates (and possibly ionizes) and the constituent species undergo additional chemical reactions. The atoms and molecules also become thermally excited as energy is transferred from the kinetic to the rotational, vibrational, and electronic modes via collisions. Our ability to understand and model and the energy state of the gas with reasonable fidelity is particularly important if it is necessary to predict the radiation energy emanating from the excited atoms and molecules from the shock layer as well as the convective heating occurring at the surface.

This complex flowfield is typically modeled in thermochemical nonequilibrium, meaning that, in addition to the conservation equations for momentum and total energy, additional equations are solved for each species in the dissociated shock-layer as well as a combined vibro-electronic energy. An excellent review of the relevant conservation equations and their required source terms for this model is presented in [4]; the results will only be briefly summarized here. In this formulation it is assumed that the vibrational and electronic modes of the gas are in equilibrium with each other, but not with the translational-rotational component. Free electrons, when present, are assumed to be in equilibrium with the vibro-electronic mode of the gas. This model therefore describes the flowfield with two temperatures; the translational-rotational (T) and the vibro-electronic (T_{ve}). Chemical reactions proceed at a finite rate, governed by the two temperatures in the flow. The energy exchange between the translational-rotational and vibrational-electronic modes is modeled using a Landau-Teller formulation assuming simple harmonic oscillators. Vibrational relaxation times are obtained from Millikan and White [5] for most species. However, relaxation times for the vibrational modes of CO₂ are taken from Camac [6], and those for CO and are taken from Park [7]. Because CO₂ and

CO relax very quickly and are dominant shock layer species, the level of thermal nonequilibrium in the flowfield is small for most cases, although it should be modeled for completeness. More complex nonequilibrium models are certainly possible, but generally the additional source terms required by such models are poorly characterized, and thus can introduce additional uncertainty into the final model. Thermodynamic properties of the component species are taken from Gordon and McBride [8].

A thorough review of the nonequilibrium chemical kinetics of a shock heated mixture of CO₂-N₂ was presented by Park et al. [7] for an 18-species gas (CO₂, NCO, CO, CO⁺, CN, NO, NO⁺, N₂, O₂, O₂⁺, C₂, N, C, C⁺, O, O⁺, Ar, e) with ionization. They proposed a 33-reaction mechanism to be used for high velocity Mars entries. Mitcheltree and Gnoffo [9] subsequently presented a reduced 8-species (CO₂, CO, NO, N₂, O₂, N, C, O) 13-reaction mechanism that neglected ionization and several other trace species. The rates for those reactions common to the Park et al. mechanism were taken directly from [7]. For entry velocities below about 8 km/s, the level of ionization in the flowfield will be small. Therefore, it is expected that the heat flux computed using the Mitcheltree and Gnoffo 8-species model should be sufficient to simulate the major characteristics of the flowfield. However, the more detailed 18-species model should be employed for cases with significant shock-layer radiation, because it includes CN (a significant radiator), as well as free electrons, which are efficient at collisional excitation of atoms and molecules. It should be noted that while the rates proposed by Park et al. were the best available at the time [7], the rates of many of these reactions have not been directly measured at conditions relevant to Martian entry. Some are estimated from indirect observations, while others are pure estimates [7], which make them potentially significant sources of uncertainty. No comprehensive sensitivity analysis of these kinetic mechanisms has been done to date.

Robust models of the transport properties of a multi-species reacting gas mixture are necessary to ensure accurate predictions of surface properties, especially heat transfer and shear stress. The viscosity and thermal conductivity of the gas mixture are typically modeled using binary collision-integral based mixing rules such as those presented by Gupta et al. [10], which have been shown to be reasonable approximations of the more accurate Chapman-Enskog relations [11]. The self-consistent effective binary diffusion (SCEBD) method [12] or equivalent [13] is used to compute the species diffusion coefficients. This method allows for the variations between the diffusion coefficients of different species to be accurately modeled without sacrificing the requirement that the diffusion velocities sum identically to zero, and has been shown [13] to accurately model the true multi-component diffusion velocities. Early simulations generally employed a constant Schmidt number based diffusion model [14]. This model, though lower in fidelity than the SCEBD approach, can produce reasonable results if the Schmidt number is tailored for the entry

conditions of interest. For weakly ionized flows the ambipolar diffusion assumption is used, and an additional correction to the diffusion fluxes is required to satisfy the requirement of zero current density in the flow [15]. These transport property expressions each require as input collision integral data for each binary interaction in the gas mixture. The best available values for the required collision integrals have been tabulated as a function of temperature in the recent critical reviews of Wright et al. [16] and Wright and Hwang [17] for all binary interactions in the mixture. These reviews include recommended values as well as estimated uncertainties for each interaction.

There are many models proposed in the literature to simulate turbulent hypersonic flows, ranging from algebraic models that estimate the eddy viscosity with a simple expression, to more complex models which require the solution of one, two, or even three additional conservation variables. For Mars entries, turbulent simulations are typically computed using either the Baldwin-Lomax algebraic turbulence model [18] or the two-equation shear stress transport (SST) model of Menter [19]. Both models include corrections for compressible flow [20]. The Baldwin-Lomax model is frequently used to compute design turbulent heating for Mars entry simulations, but its accuracy in predicting turbulent heating levels on lifting blunt cones at flight conditions is not well characterized. The SST model was shown to be reasonably accurate for a variety of hypersonic flows in a recent model validation study [20]. However, no flight data exist for validation of any turbulence model in a Martian entry environment. For turbulent flows the predicted flight heating is sensitive to the choice of the turbulent Schmidt number (Sc_T). Unfortunately, the correct value of Sc_T for high enthalpy wall-bounded flows is currently unknown. Values in the range $0.5 \leq Sc_T \leq 1.0$ are typically used, with smaller values resulting in higher heating rates. In order to conservatively bound the turbulent heating rate a value of $Sc_T = 0.5$ is recommended for design purposes.

Although several models have been proposed for estimating the onset of turbulent transition, none are well validated for blunt ablating aeroshells, particularly in a Mars environment. Schneider [21] recently published a review of flight transition data, but these results have not been used to develop new correlations at this time. Therefore, designers typically rely on simple correlations, such as a critical value of the momentum thickness Reynolds number (Re_θ) to “predict” transition in flight [22-23]. The vehicle is generally assumed to be completely turbulent once the critical value of Re_θ is reached in an attempt to ensure that the design is conservative. These approximations have not been an issue for previous Mars missions since turbulent heating was not expected, but future missions will require a more accurate assessment of turbulent transition and the resulting heating levels due to larger aeroshell size and or the use of slender mid L/D configurations. One important consideration is that the traditional Re_θ based transition criterion was developed to model smooth-body axial

transition, while in flight transition will likely be affected by distributed roughness due to ablation of the thermal protection material on the heatshield [24], or by blowing of pyrolysis gases into the boundary layer [25]. For lifting bodies at angle of attack crossflow effects can also be an important transition mechanism [22].

The separated afterbody flowfield will also likely transition from a laminar to a turbulent flow at some point during the entry. In a separated base flow, wake transition begins in the far wake and travels upstream with increasing freestream Reynolds number (Re) until reaching the neck, where it is (temporarily) stopped by the adverse pressure gradient. In the near-wake (base) region transition begins in the separation shear layer. Lees [26] gives a transition correlation for the free shear layer. This criterion is based on free-flight data, but does not include effects of upstream ablation product gas injection, which can destabilize the boundary layer and could also affect the shear layer and separated flow region. Near-wake transition can also be instigated by the ingestion of a turbulent forebody boundary layer into the wake core. Unfortunately, no validated turbulence models exist for the prediction of afterbody flowfields. Therefore, turbulent heating augmentation factors of 50-100% are typically carried as an aeroheating uncertainty margin in the design for entries where early wake transition cannot be ruled out. These factors are based on limited flight data from the Apollo and Viking missions.

Finally, it is well known that Mars is subject to planet-wide dust storms. These storms occur at irregular intervals, with an average frequency of one every 3-4 years. Given average storm duration and the residence time of dust particles in the high atmosphere after a storm has passed, prior analysis has indicated that there is a 2-4% chance of encountering significant quantities of dust during a given entry mission [27]. The possible presence of dust particles in the upper atmosphere is a concern because of the potential for mechanical erosion of the heatshield during the entry. Such erosion would need to be compensated for with additional margin. In addition, mechanical erosion may lead to a distributed roughness pattern on the TPS surface that could induce early turbulent transition or higher turbulent heating levels. Recent analysis [28] has shown that dust erosion should be negligible for moderate velocity direct entries. However, dust erosion may still be an issue for long duration (such as lifting entry or aerocapture), multiple pass, or high velocity entry trajectories.

It is important to note that the physical models discussed in this section are not the only models employed for Martian entry simulations; they are simply the models that are most commonly used by NASA and their prime contractors for entry vehicle design in recent years. The current state of the art of planetary entry aerothermal models is in a constant state of flux; as new experimental data are obtained or theoretical refinements are made the models are periodically updated. As such, the models presented here should be considered current NASA best practices, but are likely to

change in coming years, particularly in response to rigorous uncertainty and sensitivity analyses that identify the key areas for which improvements will benefit future mission design, or the future availability of engineering flight data that can be used to perform rigorous validation of the models employed.

3. SURFACE CHEMISTRY

It is well known that wall catalysis is a primary source of convective heating for many reentry applications. However, the mechanism involved in the catalytic recombination is poorly understood, in part due to difficulties in performing surface diagnostics at appropriate temperature and pressure. Consequently, modeling of catalytic reactions at the surface has been relatively primitive. Stewart [29] has characterized the catalytic properties of several NASA TPS materials in dissociated air using a combination of arc jet testing at high temperature and a side-arm reactor (diffusion tube) at low temperature. Catalytic properties of materials in dissociated CO₂ have not been characterized as extensively as in air, although some recent studies [30-33] have explored possible mechanisms on certain materials. However, none of these studies have examined materials and conditions relevant to previous or planned NASA missions. In the absence of a validated model, four simplified catalytic reaction mechanisms are commonly employed in the literature. These models are discussed briefly here.

The simplest model that is commonly used is to assume that the surface is non-catalytic. This model produces the lowest possible heating rates, and as such is not often employed for design purposes, as it is likely non-conservative. At the other extreme is the “supercatalytic” wall model [14], in which the gas composition at the wall is forced to be equal to its lowest chemical enthalpy state (in this case pure CO₂/N₂). This model is not physically based, because finite-rate surface reactions are not modeled. However, the supercatalytic assumption serves as a useful limiting case because it is conservative: essentially all of the available chemical enthalpy in the dissociated boundary layer is recovered at the wall, regardless of the actual chemical composition of the boundary layer. This was the model employed for MER and currently baselined for MSL design [23]. The Mitcheltree catalysis model [34], developed during the Mars Pathfinder program, is also often employed. In the Mitcheltree model, CO₂ recombination at the surface is modeled as a two-step reaction involving CO molecules and O atoms, with two parallel paths given by:

where (s) is a surface adsorption site and the subscript s indicates an adsorbed species. The mechanism is assumed to follow an Eley-Rideal process, in which an incident gas-phase species recombines directly with a previously adsorbed atom or molecule. The rate of recombination is bounded by the diffusion rate of the required reactants O and CO to the surface; the slower of these two processes

becomes the rate-limiting step. Potential surface reactions that form O₂ and N₂ are neglected. The heat transfer predicted by the Mitcheltree model will be close to that predicted by the supercatalytic wall for the case where the dominant boundary layer species are O and CO, but a lower heat transfer will be predicted if O₂ is present. The fourth model is based on the fact that the CO + O oxidation reaction has not been observed to occur in ground-based experiments at low temperature [30-31] and the CO + O₂ reaction mechanism is only known to occur on platinum group metals at temperatures around 250 °C [35]. Therefore this model assumes that CO₂ does not form on the surface of a TPS material at Martian entry conditions and only homogeneous surface reactions are possible, resulting in the following surface kinetics:

This model leads to significantly lower heating than the Mitcheltree or supercatalytic models, since the chemical enthalpy contained in CO molecules is not recovered at the wall. Figure 1 shows the turbulent heat transfer predicted at the peak heating point of the MSL trajectory using each of these models. The heat flux ranges from about 47 W/cm² for the non-catalytic surface to 125 W/cm² for the supercatalytic case, a factor of 2.5 difference. Clearly an improved understanding of catalytic properties for Mars entry conditions would greatly improve aeroheating prediction fidelity.

Figure 1 – Effect of catalysis on predicted turbulent centerline heating for MSL along 2009 design trajectory.

In an attempt to bound the various catalytic models previously employed, Bose and Wright [36] recently developed a simple parametric model that includes two basic reactions:

No attempt is made to simulate the details of the surface kinetics or to determine whether the Eley-Rideal or Langmuir-Hinshelwood processes are occurring. Instead, the Bose and Wright reaction mechanism [36] is modeled using two free parameters: γ_{cat} , which governs the total catalyticity of the surface via either reaction R5 or R6, and p_2 , which governs the preference of R6 over R5. Each of γ_{cat} and p_2 can vary independently from zero to one. Recombination of N atoms is neglected in this mechanism because N_2 is only a trace component of the Martian atmosphere, and remains mostly undissociated at entry velocities below about 7.5 km/s. However, N_2 recombination could be readily added to the mechanism if necessary. Figure 2 shows the computed laminar stagnation point convective heat transfer as a function of γ_{cat} for the two limiting cases of $p_2 = 0$ and $p_2 = 1$. Inspection of Fig. 2 reveals a strong “S” shaped curve in the catalytic heating as a function of γ_{cat} . This is because, as the catalyticity changes, the mechanism gradually shifts from being limited by the diffusion rate of required reactants to the surface (large γ_{cat}) to being limited by the rate of surface recombination reactions (small γ_{cat}). When using this model the Mitcheltree catalytic mechanism can be reproduced by setting $\gamma_{cat} = 1$ and $p_2 = 1$, while the homogeneous model can be reproduced (excepting the heating due to N recombination) by setting $\gamma_{cat} = 1$ and $p_2 = 0$, and the noncatalytic model is reproduced by setting $\gamma_{cat} = 0$. Note that there are currently no experimental data available to assess appropriate values for either γ_{cat} or p_2 ; the model was developed merely to parametrically bound the possible catalytic response of any thermal protection material in the hope that data for relevant materials will be forthcoming in the future.

Figure 2 - Stagnation point heat flux variation for Mars Pathfinder due to parametric variations in wall catalysis model (from [36]).

Finally, it is important to note that in the above discussion it was assumed that the TPS material response (pyrolysis, char

formation, and recession) had no influence on the aeroheating environment and surface chemical kinetics. While this assumption is approximately valid for a reusable (non-ablating) TPS, the environment for an ablating thermal protection material is much more complex and tightly coupled. As the material begins to char, pyrolyze, and eventually ablate, hydrocarbons and other product species are injected into the flow. These ablation products influence the structure of the boundary layer, affecting the convective heating rate, both locally and potentially downstream as well. The exact nature of the species emitted is dependent on the specifics of the TPS material employed. Also, as the TPS material begins to develop a surface char layer, the catalytic properties of the surface also change, and the importance of catalytic reactions, which are now competing with oxidation, nitridation, sublimation and other reactions at the surface, may be diminished [37]. A true high-fidelity surface chemistry model should include the interaction between TPS material response and the aerothermal environment via a finite-rate coupled analysis [38]. This type of analysis has not been performed to date for Mars entry conditions, mainly because the experimental data necessary to determine the rates of the required surface reactions is limited.

4. TRANSITION AND TURBULENT HEATING

Flight Predictions

Figure 3 - Predicted peak Re_θ and freestream dynamic pressure along nominal 2005 MSL design trajectory at $\alpha = 16^\circ$ (from [23]).

Forebody transition was not a concern on Viking (due to the low entry velocity), nor on MER (due to its small size). Transition was considered on Pathfinder [34], but was not a major factor influencing the final design of the TPS since no point on the body was predicted to have a fully turbulent heating level that exceed the laminar stagnation point heating. In contrast, the Mars Science Laboratory (formerly the Mars Smart Lander) is predicted to undergo turbulent

transition on the forebody early in the trajectory due to the combination of large aeroshell size (~ 4.5 m diameter), high ballistic coefficient, and non-zero angle-of-attack (~11-16 deg). Analysis in support of a potential 2005 launch predicted transition prior to peak heating [23], based on a smooth-wall momentum thickness Reynolds number based criterion ($Re_\theta = 200$). While it was recognized that surface roughness and mass injection due to TPS ablation might promote earlier transition [24], these effects were not included in the analysis because even the best-case smooth-wall correlation predicted transition well before peak heating (see Fig. 3). Therefore, from a design standpoint it was appropriate to assume a fully turbulent entry condition. At the time, the predicted peak heat flux on the leeward side of the forebody was about 65 W/cm^2 [23].

Figure 4 - Predicted laminar and turbulent centerline heating for MSL along 2009 design trajectory.

Later studies indicated that, due to design and trajectory changes, the peak predicted heating rate increased to about 125 W/cm^2 as shown in Fig. 4. This heating rate is more than twice as high as that at the cone apex ($y = 0$). These results were surprising in that such large turbulent heating augmentation factors were not expected on the leeside of a blunt lifting sphere-cone geometry, although the experience base with blunt-body entry vehicles at high Reynolds numbers and angles-of-attack is admittedly limited. If these computational predictions are accurate, the forebody thermal protection system (TPS) of the MSL mission will be sized according to the turbulent heat loads on the leeside of the forebody, rather than by those at the stagnation point. Unfortunately, until recently there has been little experimental data available to validate the computational predictions for this flow environment, which leads to large uncertainties in flight aeroheating predictions. An experimental program is currently being followed for MSL that provides much of the data needed to anchor the CFD tools and understand the physics of turbulent transition and heating augmentation for 70-deg sphere-cones.

Ground Test Data

Ground test aeroheating data fall into two broad categories: perfect gas (either air or N_2) data obtained in conventional blowdown hypersonic wind tunnels, or high-enthalpy, chemically-reacting flow data obtained in short-duration impulse (shock, reflected-shock or shock-expansion tube) facilities. Both classes of facilities have advantages and disadvantages. Conventional wind tunnels provide high-productivity, clearly defined operating conditions, and low measurements uncertainties, but operate at low enthalpies that cannot reproduce the chemical kinetics of hypervelocity atmospheric entry. These tunnels are best suited for configuration and parametric trade studies, investigation of transition phenomena, and acquisition of baseline (without chemistry) data for code validation. Impulse facilities provide high-enthalpy test environments in which the effects of chemical kinetics appropriate to re-entry conditions can be investigated in the desired test gas (e.g. CO_2 for Mars), however test uncertainties are generally higher than in conventional facilities due to lack of repeatability/ability to specify test conditions, flow establishment concerns within the limited test time (micro- to millisecond), and noise produced by the dynamic operating environment.

Figure 5 - Thermal phosphor image from LaRC Mach 6 tunnel showing turbulent transition on MSL geometry ($\alpha = 16^\circ$) caused by forebody penetrations (from [39]).

Several tests have been conducted recently in perfect-gas facilities to support the MSL mission. During the concept-development phase of MSL, the entry vehicle was to be bolted to the cruise stage through the forebody heat shield. Testing [39-40] of various bolt-hole diameters and locations in the NASA Langley 20-Inch Mach 6 Air Tunnel showed that these penetrations would produce turbulent wedges (Fig. 5) on the forebody at Reynolds numbers well below those of natural smooth-body transition. The resultant turbulent heating was found to be greater than predicted for fully turbulent flow (Fig. 6). Subsequent testing [41] of larger models in the same facility to obtain natural transition to turbulence produced data that were again under-predicted by computational methods. The reasons for this under-

prediction are not known at this time, but may point to deficiencies in the turbulence models employed.

High-enthalpy, impulse facility tests have also been conducted in the T5 shock tunnel at the California Institute of Technology [42] and the LENS shock tunnel at the CalSpan University of Buffalo Research Center [41] in support of MSL. These tests were conducted in CO₂ at enthalpies and Reynolds numbers representative of the flight environment, although the Mach number was much smaller, since much of the enthalpy in shock tunnel facilities is contained in the thermal and chemical modes of the gas, rather than the kinetic mode. Heat transfer data were obtained for laminar, transitional, and fully turbulent flows.

Figure 6 - Comparison of turbulent heating predictions with turbulent heating data from model with forebody penetrations (from [40]).

A total of twenty usable shots were obtained in T5 and twelve in LENS. The data from both facilities data clearly indicate that the leeside turbulent heating augmentation predicted by flight CFD calculations is qualitatively valid and must be accounted for during the design of the TPS. Figure 7a shows a comparison of non-catalytic (NC) and supercatalytic (SC) CFD simulations to T5 data for a laminar case. The supercatalytic simulation is in generally good agreement with the data, while the non-catalytic case significantly under-predicts the measured heating rates. Figure 7b shows a similar comparison for a case with turbulent leeside heating. Results are shown for two commonly used CFD codes (DPLR and LAURA) For this case, we see that the best agreement is achieved on the turbulent leeside ($y > 0$) when a non-catalytic wall assumption is employed, while the windside appears to remain laminar.

The trends in laminar and leeside turbulent heating shown in Fig. 7 were common across all shots in both facilities; CFD simulations were generally in good agreement with the laminar data as long as a supercatalytic wall model was employed, while turbulent simulations were in reasonable agreement when a non-catalytic wall model was used. The

reasons for this discrepancy are not known at this time. The leeside heating augmentation due to turbulence was shown to be inversely related to the freestream enthalpy. Changes in angle of attack between 11° and 16° were shown to have minimal impact on both measured and computed heat transfer for both laminar and turbulent flows. The dominant leeside transition mode was shown to be axial, rather than crossflow induced, at angles of attack up to 16°.

a)

b)

Figure 7 - Centerline heating comparison of simulation to T5 data for a) Shot 2257 ($h_0 = 11.7$ MJ/kg, $p_0 = 19.4$ MPa, $\alpha = 11^\circ$), and b) Shot 2258 ($h_0 = 4.9$ MJ/kg, $p_0 = 63.9$ MPa, $\alpha = 11^\circ$). From [41].

The data from T5 and LENS, as well as additional tests in the Langley Mach 6 air tunnel, were examined by Hollis et al. [41] in an attempt to deduce a “universal” transition correlation for transition onset on the leeside of blunt sphere-cone configurations. In general, the transition data from each facility correlated well across its range of operating conditions (Fig 8). The data in Fig. 8 are plotted in terms of an assumed transition parameter (Re_θ/M_c) vs. freestream Reynolds number (Re_∞). These axes were chosen

because they seemed to collapse the data into linear trends. However, since the value of Re_{θ} is a function of $Re_{\infty,R}$, the axes are not truly independent, and thus care should be taken when drawing conclusions based on these results. In particular, the positive slope of each transition line in Fig. 8 is not an indication that transition occurs later at higher Reynolds number.

Finally, while the results for each facility correlated well, no definitive correlation was found that could be applied across all facilities. Clearly, a much greater range of data will be required in order to resolve the effects of test gas, enthalpy-levels, chemical kinetics, facility noise, Mach and Reynolds numbers, etc. on sphere-cone transition.

Figure 8 - Correlation of leeside transition onset data from various facilities (from [41]).

In addition to the leeside transition observed in all of the tests discussed, heating augmentation that appears to correspond to some form of windside stagnation-region turbulence was also observed. This effect was clearly evident in CO_2 data from the LENS facility [41] and N_2 data from the T5 facility [43]. This phenomenon was also observed in the perfect-gas Mach 6 Air data [41], although the augmentation was much less. However, in the T5 CO_2 tests, the only limited evidence of this phenomenon was observed although the test conditions were roughly equivalent to those of the LENS CO_2 tests.

5. AFTERBODY HEATING

The current section briefly reviews attempts at simulating afterbody heating for Mars entry missions, and also discusses the use of ground-based testing in hypersonic wind tunnels to obtain useful data for model validation. Uncertainty levels associated with aeroheating predictions for the design of the afterbody of Mars entry probes are much larger than those on the forebody. These large uncertainties can have a significant impact on TPS material selection and total mass. This conservatism in the afterbody heat shield design will also shift the center of gravity aftward, which reduces static stability and in some

circumstances may necessitate the addition of ballast in the nose. A primary reason for the large uncertainty in afterbody heating predictions is a sparsity of relevant data for validation of the computational tools. Little flight data exists, particularly for Mars entry conditions (see Section 8). A recent review paper [16] summarized available sources of afterbody flight data and published attempts to reproduce these data with modern CFD. Ground test data can be helpful, but are usually complicated by sting interference effects [44-45]. Also, afterbody calculations are more complex and time consuming than forebody only simulations, because of the presence of a large separated vortical flow, which converges slowly and requires large computational grids to full resolve the necessary length scales. Until recently even axisymmetric afterbody calculations taxed the capabilities of existing computers and CFD algorithms. However, recent advances, including improved implicit algorithms and the advent of low-cost distributed memory computer clusters, has made the computation of full 3D wake flows tractable.

Base heating predictions for the Mars Pathfinder entry vehicle were made by Mitcheltree and Gnoffo [9] and Haas and Venkatapathy [46]. These calculations were some of the first applications of modern full reacting flow Navier-Stokes CFD analysis for design predictions of afterbody heating for a planetary entry spacecraft. Mitcheltree and Gnoffo performed axisymmetric calculations at the peak heating and peak dynamic pressure points on the design trajectory. Their results predicted a peak laminar afterbody heating of about 7 W/cm^2 , or about 6% of the peak forebody heating rate [9]. The maximum heating rate was observed to occur at the rear stagnation point on the flat base, and the value was predicted to be about the same at both trajectory points. Haas and Venkatapathy [46] performed similar computations at four points along the trajectory. They observed a maximum laminar afterbody heating rate of 8 W/cm^2 , which occurred at the same time as peak forebody heating. None of these calculations included the effects of turbulence, which was carried as an uncertainty factor in the final TPS design.

More recently, Edquist [47] simulated the afterbody heating of the MSL vehicle at angle of attack. These calculations are the first published design analysis of a three-dimensional Mars entry body wake flow. Predicted afterbody heating rates are generally below 3% of the forebody laminar nose cap heating rate, with the maximum normalized value occurring near the time of peak freestream Reynolds number (Fig. 9). The maximum heat flux occurs on the first afterbody windward cone at an angle of attack of 11 deg, where the flow remains attached. MSL is currently carrying an afterbody heating environments uncertainty of 200% to represent the difficulty in computing wake flowfields and estimated effects of turbulent transition. Comparisons of CFD and Viking afterbody temperature data are underway to better understand afterbody heating uncertainties [48].

Figure 9 - MSL afterbody symmetry plane heating rates normalized by nose cap laminar heating rate (from [47]).

6. SHOCK LAYER RADIATION

In general, the hypersonic shock layer for a Martian entry is in thermochemical nonequilibrium. In such a shock layer, the amount of radiation generated is governed by finite-rate processes including excitation of atoms and molecules via collisions, spontaneous or stimulated emission of photons from the excited states, and absorption of photons by other species in the shock layer. The resulting radiation spectrum is extremely non-blackbody, and is in fact dominated by strong spectral features corresponding to atomic lines and molecular bands. A true non-equilibrium radiation model must include models for all of these processes, as well as for the transport of radiation through the shock layer to the body surface. The principle radiators in a weakly ionized $\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2$ shock layer are: the CO (4+) band system, which radiates in the near ultraviolet (UV); the CN [B-X] and [A-X] band systems, which radiate in the violet and red respectively; the C_2 Swan band, which radiates in the blue-violet region, and atomic radiation, primarily from C and O atoms, which contribute some radiation in the UV, visible, and infrared (IR) portions of the spectrum. Finally, continuum radiation from bound-free and free-free transitions can become important for high entry speeds that produce ionized flow fields.

Existing Mars radiation models generally assume that the excited states of the relevant species maintain a Boltzmann distribution at the mixture electronic temperature (typically assumed to be equal to the vibrational temperature – see Section 2). A review paper by Park et al. [7] presented Boltzmann radiation calculations for a viscous non-equilibrium shock layer. The results neglected the non-adiabatic radiative cooling effect, which will reduce the radiative heat transfer since the radiative emission reduces the shock layer temperature. However, this effect is thought to be small in the nonequilibrium regime except at very high entry velocities. The Park et al. [7] results predict stagnation point radiative heating levels from 19 W/cm^2 for a sphere of 1 m radius at an entry velocity of 7 km/s to 190 W/cm^2 for a

sphere of 10 m radius at an entry velocity of 9 km/s. Hartung et al. [49] and Tauber and Sutton [50] previously published computational results for Mars shock layer radiation assuming an inviscid shock layer in thermochemical equilibrium. The inviscid equilibrium results are generally lower than the viscous nonequilibrium results due to the nonequilibrium overshoot phenomenon. Non-Boltzmann air radiation models have been developed for moderate entry velocities [51]. These models have been shown to be in reasonable agreement with available flight data from the Fire-II flight test [52], and predict much lower heating levels than those predicted using a Boltzmann assumption. Unfortunately, no such flight-validated models exist for Martian entries. However, recently Kudryavtsev et al. [53], Zalogin et al. [54], and Anohin et al. [55] have obtained shock tube data in $\text{Ar:CO}_2\text{:N}_2$ mixtures and have developed detailed kinetic models for radiation prediction. Additional ground based data, such as that obtained recently for CN radiation [56], would be of great benefit to validate the proposed models for aerothermal design.

The only Mars entry mission to date for which shock layer radiation was predicted to be significant was Mars Pathfinder. The Pathfinder probe was a 70° half-angle sphere-cone with a nose radius of 0.66 m and a diameter of 2.65 m. The entry velocity was 7.5 km/s. Pre-flight predictions of the peak radiative heating for Pathfinder ranged from about $5\text{-}12 \text{ W/cm}^2$ [9,57] compared to a predicted convective heating rate of 115 W/cm^2 and a total heating rate inferred from in situ temperature measurements of about 100 W/cm^2 [58]. Current estimates for the MSL mission indicate that less than 0.1 W/cm^2 of radiative heating will occur. However, future missions, particularly crewed entry vehicles and precursor cargo missions, may experience significant amounts of radiative heating, due to a combination of large size and high entry velocity.

7. UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS

Recent advances in computational performance have enabled much more rigorous analysis of the uncertainties associated with computational aeroheating predictions. For example, Bose et al. [59] recently introduced a technique in which parametric modeling uncertainties are determined for a given reentry problem by directly coupling a non-equilibrium CFD solver to a Monte-Carlo based statistical analysis package. A detailed uncertainty analysis of Mars Pathfinder convective entry heating was performed by Bose and Wright [36] at the peak heating point on the trajectory. Shock layer radiation, which was expected to contribute about 5% of the total heat load [57], was neglected in this analysis. In order to investigate the impact of catalysis on the overall heating uncertainty, the parametric model discussed in Section 4 above was developed and incorporated into the analysis. In this manner a structural uncertainty was parametrically bounded to that it could be explored with a standard Monte-Carlo analysis. Since the actual catalytic properties of the surface are unknown, three analyses were performed, for a highly, moderately, and

weakly catalytic wall, to capture each portion of the “S” curve in Fig. 2. In addition, a fourth analysis was performed assuming a supercatalytic wall. Each of these regions is indicated on Fig. 2.

Table 2. Pathfinder stagnation point heating

Level of Catalycity	q_w	95% confidence limits	
	(W/cm ²)	(%)	(%)
Supercatalytic	120.6	+10.3	-9.9
Highly catalytic	106.7	+12.0	-17.2
Moder. catalytic	74.0	+41.0	-33.6
Weakly catalytic	47.2	+11.7	-10.6

In addition to the two catalytic modeling parameters γ_{cat} and p_2 , a total of 128 other independent input parameters were varied, including chemical reaction rates, vibration-dissociation coupling parameters, vibrational relaxation times, and the binary collision integrals that make up mixture transport properties. A total of 3000 axisymmetric CFD runs were performed for each analysis using the 8-species Mitcheltree and Gnoffo chemistry model [9]. The key results of this study are summarized in Table 2. The nominal heating rate varied from 121 W/cm² for a supercatalytic wall to about 47 W/cm² for a weakly catalytic surface, a factor of 2.5 in the predicted heat flux. More importantly, uncertainty estimates of the heat flux were determined in each catalytic regime. It can be seen that the supercatalytic and weakly catalytic cases have roughly symmetric uncertainty distributions of approximately $\pm 10\%$ on predicted heating. On the other hand, the highly and moderately catalytic walls exhibit asymmetric uncertainty distributions. The largest uncertainties by far are for the moderately catalytic surface.

Figure 10 shows the key input contributors to the total uncertainty as determined via linear regression analysis. It is apparent that (1) only a small number of the 130 parameters are significant contributors to the uncertainty in heat flux, and (2) the relative importance of the key parameters varies considerably for the different wall catalysis assumptions. For the limiting case of a supercatalytic wall there is no variation in catalytic parameters, and nearly all of the uncertainty comes from collision integrals that govern the diffusion rate of reactants to the surface. The highly catalytic wall is in the diffusion limited regime, and thus the majority of the uncertainty again comes from collision integrals, although the preference factor p_2 is also important. For the moderately catalytic wall nearly all of the uncertainty comes from γ_{cat} , indicating that we are in a rate-limited regime at these conditions. Finally, for the weakly catalytic wall, significant uncertainty arises from collision integrals (which in this case govern the thermal conductivity of the gas), as well as a single gas-phase chemical reaction, $O_2 + O \rightleftharpoons 2O + O$, which occurs in the backward (recombination) direction in the boundary layer, affecting heat release.

Figure 10 - Principal contributors to heat flux uncertainty for a) supercatalytic, b) highly catalytic, c) moderately catalytic, and d) weakly catalytic wall assumption (from [36]).

From a design standpoint, an improved understanding of surface catalytic properties for Mars entries would have a significant impact on TPS selection and design for future missions; clearly a peak heating rate of 47 W/cm² would result in lower TPS mass and more material choices than 121 W/cm². One of the strengths of the technique presented here is that it can help to determine how much improvement is required for a given mission or material selection. For example, if focused testing (or flight data) determined that a given material performed either as a highly catalytic or

weakly catalytic surface, the current analysis indicates that further refinement in our knowledge of γ_{cat} may not be necessary, and additional research monies could be targeted to other risk drivers. However, if the material were determined to be moderately catalytic the resulting heating uncertainties could be greatly reduced if the input uncertainty of γ_{cat} were further refined.

It is important to note that the analysis presented here is only as good as the underlying physical models employed. Uncertainty analysis alone cannot characterize or bound structural uncertainties in the models; these must be exposed via ground and/or flight testing. However, sensitivity analysis can be a valuable tool to tailor such testing; if the models employed are correct the observed sensitivities should be reproducible in carefully tailored experiments. Additional analyses are planned to characterize uncertainties inherent in turbulent and radiative heating rate predictions.

8. FLIGHT DATA

The “gold standard” for validating entry aeroheating and TPS material response models is with flight data. Unfortunately such data are scarce for non-Earth entries, and the recent trend is to eliminate engineering instrumentation from planetary entry missions as a cost saving measure. For example, the MER landers included no instrumentation, and none is currently planned for either Phoenix in 2007 or MSL in 2009. A small amount of engineering flight data is available from two previous Mars missions: Viking and Pathfinder. In addition, the MER Opportunity rover conducted a visual observation campaign of its aeroshell in early 2005 as part of its extended mission. These data sources are briefly discussed below.

Mars Viking I & II

The Viking program included two landers that entered the Martian atmosphere in July and September of 1976. Both probes were 70° sphere-cones with an ablative forebody heatshield made of SLA-561, which was injected into a phenolic fiberglass honeycomb structure. The Viking probes flew a lifting entry at a nominal angle of attack of 11° , and entered at a relative velocity of about 4.5 km/s [60]. There was no instrumentation on the forebody aeroshell, but each probe included a base pressure sensor and two surface-mounted aftbody temperature sensors – one on the fiberglass inner cone and one on the aluminum skin of the outer cone [61], as shown in Fig. 11. The base pressure sensor was actually inside the aeroshell, which was vented. Three of the four temperature sensors worked correctly, but the sensor on the aluminum outer cone of the Viking I entry vehicle failed near the peak heating point [61]. Pre-flight analysis predicted afterbody heating to be 3% of the forebody stagnation point heating rate [61], but flight data indicated that the peak heating was actually more than 5% of the stagnation value. The high heating levels, as well as the slope change observed in heating rate vs. Reynolds number at $Re_D \sim 5 \times 10^5$, were believed to be evidence of

turbulent transition on the base [62]. These data have not been used for high-fidelity model validation to date; however an upcoming paper [48] will explore the ability of modern computational methods to reproduce the flight data.

Figure 11 - Schematic of Viking entry configuration showing afterbody thermocouple locations (from [60]).

Mars Pathfinder

Mars Pathfinder successfully entered the Martian atmosphere on July 4, 1997 on a ballistic trajectory at a relative velocity of 7.5 km/s [63]. The forebody TPS for this mission was SLA-561V, nearly identical to that employed on Viking [64]. The afterbody was protected by SLA-561S, a spray-on version of the forebody material.

Figure 12 - Mars Pathfinder schematic drawing, showing instrument locations (from [57]). Instruments are not coplanar.

The aeroshell was instrumented with nine thermocouples (TC) at various depths in the TPS material and three platinum resistance thermometers (PRT), as shown in Fig. 12. Six of the nine thermocouples returned usable data, although the results from the forebody TC's are somewhat ambiguous due to anomalous behavior of the PRT's used to

calibrate the TC data [58]. The only post-flight analysis of these data to date was performed by Milos et al. [58] using loosely coupled axisymmetric CFD and material response calculations. Forebody results showed that the measured temperatures were consistent with a total incident aeroheating about 85% of the fully catalytic value at the stagnation point and shoulder. Detailed calculations were not performed on the afterbody; however Milos et al. [58] showed that measured temperatures implied incident heating rates that were significantly lower than pre-flight predictions [9].

Mars Exploration Rovers – Opportunity

The twin MER spacecraft entered the Martian atmosphere in January 2004. Once again, the forebody TPS was SLA-561V, and the afterbody was protected with SLA-561S. Although neither aeroshell included any flight instrumentation, a unique opportunity afforded itself after both rovers lasted well beyond their planned lifetimes. During their extended missions, it was proposed that the Opportunity rover drive to a location near the discarded forebody heatshield and conduct visual observations with the cameras and micro-imager in an attempt to deduce its performance during the entry [65]. The MER heatshield observation campaign included imagery of the TPS char layer, main seal, substructure, and thermal blankets. Although detailed imagery was difficult due to the fact that the aeroshell inverted and broke into multiple pieces on impact with the Martian surface, good data were obtained at several locations. Figure 13 shows a sample of the type of image obtained. This image depicts a section of the heatshield that was originally near the shoulder of the spacecraft. This section of the heatshield was broken upon impact, allowing the camera to take a cross sectional view if the carbon polyimide face sheets, aluminum honeycomb substructure, and TPS material. A detailed analysis of the data has not been performed to date, but such analysis is planned during 2006.

Figure 13 - Cross sectional view of the MER-B heatshield on the surface of Mars, obtained with the camera on the Opportunity rover (from [65]).

9. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The current state of the art for computational and experimental aerothermal analysis for Mars entry missions is reviewed. The aeroheating environment of all Mars missions to date has been dominated by laminar convective heating. The primary uncertainty in our ability to predict forebody laminar convective heating is surface catalysis in a CO₂ environment. The status of model development and ground-based testing in this area is briefly reviewed. Current design models assume a conservative upper limit for catalytic heat transfer, which implies that significant performance gains may be possible if this effect were better characterized. Upcoming missions, including the Mars Science Laboratory in 2009, will experience early transition to turbulence due to a combination of large size and high ballistic coefficient. Transition location and the resulting turbulent heating levels on the blunt, lifting cones employed for entry are another large source of uncertainty. Future missions, particularly crewed vehicles, will encounter additional heating from shock-layer radiation due to a combination of larger size and faster entry velocity. Unlike the case for Earth entries, no validated model for shock layer radiation in a CO₂ environment currently exists, although some recent developments in the Russian literature are discussed. The applicability of a rigorous Monte-Carlo methodology for identifying and quantifying the sensitivities and uncertainties inherent in the physical models employed to predict these phenomena is introduced. Results for Mars Pathfinder indicate that the majority of the prediction uncertainty in laminar convective aeroheating is due to poor knowledge of the catalytic mechanism, as well as uncertainties in several key collision integrals which are used to determine transport properties. The need for fully coupled analysis that combines TPS material response and aerothermal prediction uncertainties is identified. Capabilities of ground test facilities to support aeroheating validation are also summarized. In particular, shock tunnels, which can produce flight-like enthalpy and Reynolds numbers, are shown to have value for code validation purposes, although transition data from such facilities are difficult to characterize due to tunnel noise effects. Finally, engineering flight data from the Viking and Pathfinder missions, as well as imagery from the MER-B heatshield observation campaign, are discussed. These data clearly have utility for code validation studies, although minimal effort has been expended to date on this activity.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank Christine Szalai (JPL) for information about and images from the MER-B heatshield observation campaign.

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